

A Study on Nifty 50 during COVID 19 Pandemic

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Abstract: This study aims to understand the performance of Nifty 50 during COVID-19 pandemic. The paper attempts to predict the post COVID-19 second wave value of the Nifty 50 and check the efficiency of ARIMA model in short duration. To study and forecast the performance of Nifty 50 daily closing prices of Nifty 50 index is considered. The historical data are collected from NSE's website. Analysis shows that index has given immense opportunities during the COVID 19 pandemic to enter in equity market. The ARIMA model indicates the range bound movement with 95 per cent of confidence interval.

Keywords: Equity Index, Nifty, Forecasting, ARIMA Modelling

JEL Classification Number: G10, G11 and G17

1. Introduction

The Nifty 50 is a leading benchmark indicator index on Indian stock market. It consists of top 50 Indian companies listed on NSE; it is the weighted average of all selected largest Indian companies. National Stock exchange of India Ltd. was established in year 1992. The Nifty 50 index has gone up significantly for the time period of study as can be seen from chart 1. Chart 2 shows the first difference. The value of index has risen from 6144 in year 2008 to 10980 in year 2019. The major rise can be seen in the year 2009-10. However, the volatility in prices can be seen due to global factors affecting the emerging market equity prices. The index has surged significantly from lower levels from March-April 2020 to June 2021. It rose from 7511 levels in March 2020 to 15800 levels in month of June 2021. It has rose more than one hundred per cent within a short duration of a year only. Giving opportunities to investors to enter in equity markets, this can be clearly observed in graph above. The Nifty 50 is constituted by top fourteen sector representatives consists of 50 most liquid equity shares traded on NSE India's platform.

2. Review of Literature

To forecast the Nifty 50 index ARIMA model is applied here. The research work done by Adebisi (2014) and Singh et. al. (2019) used ARIMA model to forecast the time series has been reviewed. The econometric time series models and its applications are referred from Brook (2014). To forecast the time series with the linear model, stationarity is basic

assumption and to check the stationarity of the series. Dickey (1979) developed the test to check the unit root in series, the test is popularly known as ADF test. Research paper published by Ashik et. al. (2017) forecasted Nifty Bank using ARIMA model using daily closing prices of bank nifty. Dhyani (2020) also attempted to forecasted stock market using ARIMA modelling, here also Nifty 50 was forecasted. Another research paper published in Solanki (2017) has estimated the mustard prices using ARIMA model. Paper published by Umadevi (2013) also predicted value for Midcap index using ARIMA model.

Chart 1: Time plot - Nifty 50

Chart 2: Time plot - First order differencing on Nifty 50

It is important to study the performance of equity markets and forecast it. The research models are also available to test the same, but performance of those models is always doubtful in uncertain situations, particularly in the current uncertain global pandemic COVID 19 situation. This research is designed to understand the Nifty 50 and its movement during COVID-19 Pandemic and to estimate and forecast the short-term levels of Nifty 50 index using ARIMA model. The research hypotheses are follows.

NH-1: There is unit root, and the series is non-stationary.

NH-2: The model is not accurate to forecast the value of time series.

3. Data and Methodology

Secondary data sources are used to carry out this research study. Total of 3567 data points of main equity index are taken into consideration for study purpose.

Equity index data for Nifty 50 are taken from the website of National Stock Exchange. 3567 observations from 2007 to June 2021 were taken based on daily closing price of Nifty 50.

Graphical representations and comparative tools are used to understand the pattern of Nifty 50 index, while ARIMA model has been employed to forecast the time series.

Table 1: Weightages of Sectors in Nifty 50

Sr. No.	Sector	Weight (%)	Sr. No.	Sector	Weight (%)
1.	Financial services	34.96	8.	Construction	2.39
2.	Oil and Gas	15.74	9.	Metals	2.34
3.	IT	15.27	10.	Cement and Cement Products	2.04
4.	Consumer Goods	12.15	11.	Power	1.91
5.	Automobiles	5.82	12.	Fertilizers and Pesticides	0.58
6.	Pharma	2.98	13	Services	0.55
7.	Telecom	2.89	14	Media and Entertainment	0.38

Source: https://www.niftyindices.com/Factsheet/ind_nifty50.pdf

4. Data Analysis

Data for Nifty 50 has been checked for price change over previous year on YoY basis. Table 2 shows the percentage change over previous year based on closing price of the given date. The drastic volatility is observed during year 2007 and 2010 following the US subprime crisis and its recovery. Nifty has given almost 8.5 percent CAGR return since 2007 till August 2019 and period of study. Return from Nifty 50 became volatile following the US subprime crisis. The same has decreased gradually and reached at 10910 in January 2019 giving 4.5 percent returns since January 2018.

Table 2: Percent Change in Nifty 50 on YoY basis

Date	Closing Price	YoY Change (%)	Date	Closing Price	YoY Change (%)
1-Jan-08	6144.35	53.3251	1-Jan-16	7963.2	-3.8725
1-Jan-09	3033.45	-50.6303	2-Jan-17	8185.8	2.7953
1-Jan-10	5201.05	71.4565	1-Jan-18	10435.55	27.4835
1-Jan-11	6134.5	17.9473	1-Jan-19	10910.1	4.54743
2-Jan-12	4624.3	-24.6181	1-Jan-20	12182.50	11.6625
1-Jan-13	5950.85	28.6865	23-Mar-20	7610.0	-37.5333
1-Jan-14	6301.65	5.89495	1-Jan-21	14018.50	84.2115
1-Jan-15	8284	31.4576	1-Jun-21	15574.85	11.1021

Note: Data points are considered for previous closing day for holidays falling on some of the above dates Source: Author’s Calculation.

4.1 ARIMA Model

An Auto regressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) model is usually stated as ARIMA (p,d,q). Future value of time series can be estimated based on the current observations after identification of model. This process is also known as Box-Jenkins method. The non-seasonal stationary series can be constructed with different combinations of past value and the error terms. This can be symbolised as ARIMA (p, d, q) and can be represented as:

$$y_t = c + \phi_1 y_{t-1} + \phi_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p y_{t-p} + e_t - \theta_1 e_{t-1} - \theta_2 e_{t-2} - \dots - \theta_q e_{t-q}$$

4.2. Summary statistics for Nifty 50 observations

There are no outliers observed for the study period from January 2007 to June 2021 of Nifty 50 index. The summary statistics can be observed through the table 3, it consists of Minimum and Maximum, S.D, Mean and Median of all the observations. The observations cover daily closing prices of Nifty 50 index.

Table 3: Summary Statistics using the observations 2007-06-02 - 2021-06-07

Variable	Mean	Median	S.D.	Min	Max
Closing Price	7484.5	6483.1	2877.3	2524.2	15752.0

Table 4: The output of ADF Unit Root Test at level and first order difference

	ADF Test Statistics		P value	
	C	C&T	C	C&T
At Level	0.5734	-2.0528	0.9891	0.5716
At First Difference	-16.3114	-16.3724	0.000	0.000

Note: C indicates the constant and C&T indicates constant and trend. Source: Author’s Calculations using EViews.

4.3. Stationarity Check of data

The time series plot is used to understand the stationarity of the series. The series consists of daily basis Nifty 50 closing prices from January 2007 to June 2021. The time series plot clearly indicates the non stationary trend. In the given Box-Jenkins method, to make series stationary, first order differencing is used. To make series stationary the series has been differentiated once. The differencing data series plot depicts the stationarity of the time series.

To confirm the stationarity of the series Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root test is employed here. Further, plotting of ACF and PACF suggest the value of p and q is almost 1 and 2 respectively and hence AR(1) and MA(2) model was considered. Different combinations of ARIMA models were compared and ARIMA (1,2,2) model was selected, considering the lowest value of AC - Akaike criterion. Chart 3(a) shows the correlogram for ACF and PACF. This indicates the random non seasonality of series while the first order differencing of Nifty 50 is shown in chart 3(b). Considering all 3567 observations (daily closing price of Nifty 50) the coefficient for constant is 1.464 with p-value of 0.1431, coefficient for AR(1) is -0.9084 with p value <0.0001 and -0.9230 coefficient for MA(2) and p-value <0.0001. This shows the best fit model ARIMA (1, 2, 2).

Chart 3 (a): Time plot - Nifty 50

Chart 3 (b): ACF and PACF - First order differencing on Nifty 50

Source: Author’s Calculations using EViews Software.

Table 5: ARIMA, using observations 2-3093 (T = 3567)

	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	p-value
Const	0.0022	0.0015	1.464	0.1431
phi_1	-0.9084	0.0775	-11.71	<0.0001***
theta_1	-0.0769	0.0788	-0.9758	0.3292
theta_2	-0.9230	0.0777	-11.86	<0.0001***
Mean dependent var	0.0181		S.D. dependent var	132.6534
Mean of innovations	-0.4646		S.D. of innovations	94.1603
Log-likelihood	-21277.45		Akaike criterion	42564.90
Schwarz criterion	42595.80		Hannan-Quinn	42575.92

Note: Best fit ARIMA (1,2,2), Model**Significance between 1 and 5 percent, *** Statistical significance at the 1 percent level.

The lowest value of AIC for ARIMA (1,2,2) is 42564.90. The other ARIMA models such as ARIMA (1,1,1), ARIMA (1,1,2) and ARIMA (1,2,1) fails to estimate the value of series as it resulted in non-significance of AR and MA legs with higher value of AIC of the models. Now from estimated ARIMA (1,2,2) model the value of series can be forecasted. The output for 95 per cent confidence interval prediction, standard error and 95 per cent interval can be generated for next ten observations; the same can be seen from table 6. From table 5, observation 3568 - 3577 can be forecasted as seen in predication value with 95 per cent of confidence interval.

Table 6: ARIMA (1,2,2) Forecasts Value, 95% confidence intervals, z (0.025) = 1.96

Obs.	Close	Prediction	Std. Error	95% interval	Actual Close
3568	15670.25	15697.62	-	-	-
3569	15751.65	15677.19	-	-	-
3570	Undefined	15760.38	94.160	15575.82 - 15944.93	15740.10
3571	Undefined	15766.40	134.136	15503.50 - 16029.30	15635.35
3572	Undefined	15774.88	163.958	15453.53 - 16096.23	15737.75
3573	Undefined	15781.13	189.702	15409.32 - 16152.94	15799.35
3574	Undefined	15789.42	211.888	15374.12 - 16204.71	15811.85
3575	Undefined	15795.86	232.342	15340.48 - 16251.24	15869.25
3576	Undefined	15803.98	250.816	15312.39 - 16295.57	15767.55
3577	Undefined	15810.58	268.291	15284.74 - 16336.42	15691.40
3578	Undefined	15818.56	284.463	15261.02 - 16376.10	15683.35
3579	Undefined	15825.29	299.965	15237.37 - 16413.21	15746.50
3580	Undefined	15833.17	314.529	15216.70 - 16449.63	15772.75

Source: Author’s Calculation.

5. Findings

CNX Nifty 50 Index is a well-diversified set of fifty companies and reflects the overall market condition. The data series is found to be non- stationary and hence the series is differentiated of first order to make it stationary. Nifty has given approximately 10 per cent CAGR returns since 2007 and has doubled since March 2020 lows. ACF and PACF suggest the lag of 1 for AR and lag of 2 for MA hence AR(1) and MA(2) are recommended. Hence, the ARIMA (1,2,2) model for series is suggested to estimate time series. Here observations from 3570 to 3580 are forecasted values indicated in table 6. The same forecast range can be observed from chart4 at 95 per cent confidence.

Chart 4: Nifty 50 forecast value for 95% confidence

Source: Author’s Forecast using EViews.

6. Conclusions

We can draw conclusions that Nifty 50 has recovered substantially from record lows levels of 7511 in March 2020, when lockdowns were ordered due to spread of COVID 19 Pandemic in the country. The major movement in index can be explained by top ten stocks of index. The remaining 40 shares has weightage of 38 percent. All the actual post forecasted values are in the range of 95 per cent interval only. Analysis shows the movement of actual prices as well as forecasted value through ARIMA model. All actual closing prices are within the forecasted range only; hence ARIMA (1,2,2) model is found to be efficient and accurate to forecast Nifty 50. The ARIMA (1,2,2) is suggested here

estimate the time series and the same can be used to forecast the Nifty 50 index. Similarly, the future projections can be made considering 95 percent confidence interval.

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